

THE EFFECT OF DECONSOLIDATION ON INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH FOR THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *consolidation, compaction, de-consolidation, thermoplastic composite*

1 Introduction and Fundamentals

In the last decade thermoplastic composites has been identified as an important low weight and high strength engineering material. Especially their possibility of re-melting draws a high interest [1, 2]. Nevertheless, the re-melting can cause positive effects such as weldability and formability or negative effects like residual stresses and a loss of consolidation of the well-consolidated composite, which is dependent on the heating procedure. Henninger et al. defined deconsolidation as the tendency of a composite to lose consolidation on re-heating, hence as a structural degradation. The degradation is associated with an increase of void content [3]. Deconsolidation is commonly unwanted due to the increased void content leading to a reduction of mechanical performance of parts [4-6]. Therefore, the pressure must be kept until the composite solidifies to prevent deconsolidation. Many authors have investigated the factors influencing the deconsolidation terms void content and thickness. From the literature, different main factors can be identified. One key factor can be the decompaction of the fiber reinforcement network [4]. Another factor is the evolution of the voids caused by the thermal gas expansion and internal void pressure [5, 6]. The surface tension is leading to void shrinkage and coalescence of smaller voids into larger voids [5, 6]. Further factors are the thermal expansion of the composite itself and the viscoelastic behavior of the matrix [7]. The importance of each factor is controversial due to the different investigated composite types.

Usually the studies were addressed to the thickness increase and void evolution dependent on some of the listed influencing parameters. But nevertheless only Henninger et. al has investigated the effect of de-consolidation on interlaminar properties [3]. They investigated the effect of holding pressure on

the flexure strength, which is rather linear for a GF/PA12 and decreases by about 30% from 2% void content to 10%. Two reasons were identified of influencing the interlaminar shear strength, namely the polymer strength and the void content. Many authors has investigated the influence of void content on interlaminar shear strength and showed a district linear behavior over a wide range of void content up to 14% [8-12]. The determined constants varied from author to author, which indicates that the influence is material or geometry dependent. John and Brown proposed an influence of the sizing, which is leading to a weaken of interface between the fibers and polymer resulting in lower interlaminar shear strength [13]. Vina et. al investigated the effect of moisture on interlaminar shear strength and found a significant decrease of strength even after short exposure times [14]. In order to get a deeper knowledge on the effect of deconsolidation on the interlaminar behavior, many different materials were investigated in respect to void content and interlaminar strength.

2 Materials

Several carbon and glass fiber composite materials were investigated with different weave styles and polymers such as polypropylene (high crystalline), polyphenylsulfide (medium crystalline), and polycarbonate (amorphous). It is aimed to cover a wide range of materials in order to gain a basic understanding about mechanisms and effects of deconsolidation. Therefore, the composites were manufactured in an autoclave or with a hot press, to indicate a possible influence of the manufacturing process. Three different reinforcement types are used, an unidirectional glass fiber, a 1/4 satin glass fiber weave, and a 2x2 twill carbon fiber weave. More details are given in Table 1. As matrix a polypropylene from Borealis AG type PP BJ100HP,

a polycarbonate from Bayer Material Science AG, and a polyphenylsulfide from Chevron Phillips chemical Company LLC type Ryton® are used (Table 2). The composites were manufactured in a film-stacking layout impregnated in an autoclave and with a hot press. All specimens were heated and cooled with 10 K/min to target temperature. During the autoclave process a pressure of 2.4 MPa and while the hot pressing a pressure of 4.5 MPa were applied. The polypropylene composite was heated to 210 °C and held on temperature for 1 h. The polyphenylsulfide was heated to 320 °C, and the polycarbonate specimens were heated to 280 °C respectively. All used materials and their acronym are listed in Table 3.

3 Research Target and Approach

A three-step approach was chosen including a thickness measurement, an optical investigation of micrographs, and a mechanical measurement according to DIN EN ISO 14130. In the first step, the thickness and the fiber volume fraction was determined by high-resolution measurements. This is very important, because the fiber volume fraction increases the decompaction force with a polynomial function of the fourth order [15]. In the second step the consolidated and deconsolidated void distribution and content was analyzed to determine void migration and coalescence. Fig.1 shows the void change of a micrograph exemplary for GF/PC.

Finally, the interlaminar shear strength and the fracture type were determined. Mechanical experiments showed a high impact on the thickness and interlaminar shear strength of a glass fiber polypropylene composite with an initial fiber volume fraction of about 53%. The fracture behavior changed from a more brittle to a more plastic deformation.

In order to get equal matrix strength, the crystallinity kept similar by means of constant cooling rate of 10 K/min after manufacturing and deconsolidation likewise. This was confirmed by a differential scanning calorimetry analysis.

3.1 Deconsolidation treatment

Deconsolidation treatments were carried out on a heated tool. Only from the bottom, heat was applied to the specimen. A cap covered the specimens to homogenize the temperature distribution of the

specimen. Each specimen had a size of 50x50 mm². Free deconsolidation experiments were carried out for each configuration. During testing no external pressure was applied. This treatment was repeated for each configuration three times. Therefore, the specimens were heated with 10 K/min to target temperature, which are 210 °C for PP, 320 °C for PPS, and 280 °C for PC. The specimens were held for 30 min on temperature for relieving all internal pressure and equilibrate the specimen in the deconsolidated state. Inhibit deconsolidation treatments were carried out while applying a defined force. The experimental set up was similar to the free deconsolidation treatment, in contrast on top of the specimen a weight was loaded to gain a new equilibrated state of the deconsolidation, which has a lower void content than the freely deconsolidated specimens do. The test was not repeated, because only a trend is aimed to show. The applied pressure was set to 0.0016 MPa, 0.0048 MPa, 0.0064 MPa, and 0.012 MPa, which are lower than the proposed pressure of 0.2 MPa to eliminate deconsolidation for some reported fabrics in literature [16, 17].

3.2 Analysis approach

The thickness of the specimen was measured before and after each treatment with a high precise measurement screw with an proposed accuracy of $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$. At four positions, the thickness was measured. The fiber volume fraction was determined by the initial thickness, the number of layers, and the reinforced configuration.

Micrographs of the consolidated and deconsolidated specimens were taken for post optical analysis. This analysis gained the void content, the void size distribution, the void shape, and the average void radius.

Interlaminar shear strength was determined by the short-beam method according to DIN EN ISO 14130. The bearing distance was chosen for each specimen according the specimen's thickness as required by the standard. This requires adjustments of the bearing distance several times. The displacement velocity was set to 10 mm/min. The tested specimens were optically investigated to define the fracture type.

4 Results

4.1 Thickness analysis (free deconsolidation)

The thickness measurements are shown in Fig. 2 for the reinforced polypropylene specimens. The unidirectional reinforced specimen indicates a moderate thickness increase due to their good alignment and packaging of the rovings and filaments next to each other. The specimens with a fabric as reinforcement exhibit a higher thickness increase. An additional increase of thickness can be observed at an increased fiber volume fraction, which can be more than 20% of the total thickness. This result corresponds well with findings of Yu et. al [7], who had identified the fiber reinforcement network as the driving factor of deconsolidation. Further analysis was carried out for polyphenylsulfide and polycarbonate. The results (see Fig. 3) indicate a similar tendency of the thickness increase with the fiber volume content and the type of reinforcement. Only the polycarbonate specimens showed a significant different behavior. According to the datasheet, the specimens take 0.12% moisture at 23°C and 50% humidity. This corresponds to the weight measurement of the specimens before and after drying (0.116%). The moisture has a conspicuous impact on the thickness increase during deconsolidation due to vaporization of the absorbed water.

4.2 Void analysis

Micrographs of the consolidated and deconsolidated specimens were taken and are illustrated exemplarily in Fig. 1. The voids are mainly distributed between the layers of the fabric or yarn. This will increase the volume between the layers, where the voids cannot transfer any loads between the layers as well as it acts as a notch causing a decrease of interlaminar fracture strength depending on the ductility and strength of the polymer. Mostly spherical or more rarely elliptical voids occur. A void distribution analysis is carried out to determine the void formation before and after the deconsolidation treatment. The area of each void class in percent is illustrated in Fig. 5 exemplary for PP3 HP 52. Initially an average void radius of 3.2 μm can be calculated and no large voids occurred. After deconsolidation a new maxima occurred at the class 118 μm. This distribution is typical for the other specimens, too and a conspicuous void radius

increase occurred after deconsolidation. The void content evolution of the deconsolidation treated specimen with different pressures revealed as expected a strong influence on the applied pressure (Fig 5). The void content decrease until a critical pressure is reached; after that no significant decrease appeared. This is 0.012 MPa for the 1/4 satin glass fiber reinforced polypropylene for 48% and 49% fiber volume content and 0.025 MPa for a higher fiber volume content of 53%. 1/4 satin glass fiber reinforced polyphenylsulfide with a fiber volume content 52% exhibits a similar critical pressure of about 0.025 MPa. The critical pressure is an order of magnitudes lower than the applied pressure during standard manufacturing or forming processes.

4.3 Mechanical analysis

ILSS test according to DIN EN ISO 14130 were carried out, in order to investigate the decrease of interlaminar shear strength with an increase of thickness and an increase of void content respectively. In order to investigate the deconsolidation on different levels, four different counter forces were applied during the deconsolidation treatment. Due to the relative low counter forces no matrix squeeze out occurred, which would falsify the results due to mass losses inside the composite. The force inhabits deconsolidation and creates a new equilibrium resulting in a different void contents. The graphs (Fig. 6) confirm the findings that the decrease of interlaminar shear strength is linear with an increase of void content. This was also found by Henninger et. al [3] for a glass fiber reinforced polyamide 12. The results for free deconsolidation experiments of the reinforced polypropylene are shown in Fig. 7 and for the reinforced polyphenylsulfide specimens in Fig. 8. The level of interlaminar shear strength is higher due to the high strength of the matrix. However, the decrease of interlaminar shear strength with an increase of void content is stronger pronounced caused by the low fracture elongation of polyphenylsulfide comparing to polypropylene, which is not so fragile against notches. The specimens before and after deconsolidation show a linear decrease of interlaminar shear strength. The slope is similar but they have other intersection with the y-axis. The unidirectional reinforced specimens show the lowest level of interlaminar shear strength caused by the clear straight interface between the

layers. The 2x2 twill carbon fabric has the highest interlaminar shear strength. The fabric has an open structure, which means they have spaces between the yarns. This structure accelerates nesting of the layer into each other resulting in a highly interlocking interface between the layers.

The fracture type of the polypropylene specimens and polycarbonate specimens exhibits showed a mixture type of compression and deformation. Only the polyphenylsulfide specimens broke interlaminar in the consolidated state and deformed in the deconsolidated state.

The force displacement curve for PC 3 is shown in Fig. 9 for the consolidated and free deconsolidated state. The fracture force decreases from 2614 N to 1971 N. In contrast to the elongation at fracture, which increases from 0.44 mm to 1.14 mm. Two main changes occurred for polyphenylsulfide and polycarbonate specimens. First the post fracture behavior changes from a drop of force after fracture in the consolidated state to a drift of elongation on the fracture force level for the deconsolidated specimens. These specimens deformed until the die ran into the rig. No drop of force occurred. Second the elongation at fracture was analyzed for all specimens to gain more information about the fracture type and mechanisms (see Fig. 10 and 11). In contrast to the expectation, the increase of void content and therefore an increase of notch size lead to a more ductile fracture. The elongation at fracture increases for the polypropylene specimens from about 0.2 mm to more than 0.4 mm whether if they are fabric or unidirectional reinforced. Voids cannot transfer loads and acts as notches, which would suggest a lower strength resulting in a lower elongation at fracture. Nevertheless, the distance between the layers is also increased leading to a longer deformation path way. Plastic deformation can dissipate the shift of the layers to each other during bending the specimen. These newfound abilities (elongation at fracture and the post fracture behavior) could be useful for energy dissipation applications, due to their plastic deformation. More research is necessary to quantify this ability and their limitation. However, this behavior was unknown especially for composites with polyphenylsulfide matrixes.

5 Discussion

As shown in the previous section and in literature deconsolidation decreases the interlaminar shear strength. It can be formulated in Eq.1, where τ is the interlaminar shear strength, A and B are constants, and ϕ is the void content.

$$\tau = A + B * \phi \quad (1)$$

A can be associated as an ideal interlaminar shear strength of the composite in a void free condition. The void free interlaminar shear strength, the dependency of interlaminar shear strength on the void content, the void content at full deconsolidation, and the interlaminar shear strength at full deconsolidation are listed for all used configurations in Table 4. The ideal interlaminar shear strength is dependent on the polymer strength and stiffness and the reinforcement including the fiber volume fraction, the reinforcement type, and the lay up. It is interesting to note that the specimen PPS 2 52 and 53 have a similar fiber volume fraction but PPS 2 52 has a significant lower strength. The reason is the stacking sequence. PPS 2 53 has a cross ply lay up and PPS 2 52 has parallel ply lay up. Due to the orientation of the satin weave the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ has a better ability of nesting, which creates a more undulated interlayer that inhibit fracture propagation.

B is the dependency of the interlaminar shear strength on the void content and on the polymer only. It is independent from the stacking sequence, the fiber volume fraction, reinforcement type, fiber type, and manufacturing process as shown in the previous chapter.

Deconsolidation is commonly an undesired effect due to the negative effect on mechanical properties like interlaminar strength. Nevertheless, Hagstrand et. al found a positive effect of void content increase associated to a higher thickness by constant mass. The void content leads to a decrease in interlaminar strength but also the higher thickness leads to a higher moment of inertia resulting in a higher beams stiffness and a minor higher flexural load (the flexure strength is decreased!) [8]. Another positive effect is the higher deformation of the specimen during interlaminar testing and the different fracture type of the polyphenylsulfide specimens. Due to

the higher deformation, a larger area is subjected to the load. The higher area can dissipate more energy by crack propagation. That can increase damage tolerance behavior, but it must be pointed out that the low strength will lead to an earlier start of failure, which is usually undesired. More research is necessary to gain a better understanding of this effect.

6 Conclusions

The effect of reinforcement configuration, polymer, manufacturing process on void content, and interlaminar shear strength in the deconsolidated state is summarized in Table 5.

Deconsolidation leads to a distinct increase of void content, where the driving factor is the fiber reinforcement network. Especially the fiber volume fraction and reinforcement type (UD or weave) determines the thickness increase and therefore the void content. The void distribution changes from many small void in the consolidated state to small void and some very large voids in the deconsolidate state. They mainly occur in the interlayer of the plies. The effect of void content on interlaminar shear strength is linear decreasing with an increasing void content, which confirms the literature where different initial void contents in the consolidated were investigated. The ideal interlaminar shear strength in the void free condition is dependent on the fiber reinforcement, the stacking sequence, and the polymer. A high fiber or ply interlocking increases the ideal interlaminar shear strength. This can be achieved by the stacking sequence or the reinforcement type. In addition, high polymer strength improves the interlaminar shear strength. The polymer only determines the dependency of the interlaminar shear strength on the void content. Polypropylene exhibits a decrease in average of 0.51%, polyphenylsulfide of 1.03%, and polycarbonate of 1.31%. This is far lower than for more brittle polymers like thermosets (epoxy 4-7% [8-12]) decrease the shear strength per percentage void content. That means thermoplastic polymer have a weaker dependency of interlaminar shear strength on void content than thermoset polymer. Therefore, higher void contents could be acceptable for thermoplastic composite than for thermoset composites.

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Fig. 1 Example of a consolidated and deconsolidated GF/PC

Fig. 2 The thickness of consolidated and free deconsolidated polypropylene

Fig. 3 The thickness of consolidated and free deconsolidated polyphenylsulfide and polycarbonate

Fig. 4 Example of an area change of each void class dependent on void radius in percent for PP3 HP 52

Fig. 5 Dependency of void content on applied pressure during deconsolidation

Fig. 6 Dependency of interlaminar shear strength on void content for polypropylene

Fig. 7 Loss of interlaminar shear strength with void content increase for polypropylene

Fig. 8 Loss of interlaminar shear strength with void content increase for polyphenylsulfide and polycarbonate

Fig. 9 Force displacement curve for PC 3 in the consolidated and free deconsolidated state

Fig. 10 Elongation at fracture of consolidated and deconsolidated polypropylene

Fig. 11 Elongation at fracture of consolidated and deconsolidated polyphenylsulfide and polycarbonate

Table 1. Reinforcement properties used in this study

Reinforcement type	Fiber type	Surface density (g/m ²)	Yarn density (Yarns/cm)	Linear density (g/km)
Unidirectional	Glass	456	4	1088
1/4 Satin	Glass	300	22	68
2x2 Twill	Carbon	200	5	200

Table 2: Polymer properties

Polymer type	Tensile strength [MPa]	Tensile Modulus [GPa]	Elongation at breakage [%]	Density [kg/cm ³]
Polypropylene	25	1300	-	0.9
Polyphenylsulfide	86	3800	3	1.35
Polycarbonate	66	2400	6	1,2

Table 3. Materials used in this study

Reinforcement type	Fiber type	Matrix	Initial fiber volume fraction	Manufacturing process	Acronym
Uni-directional	Glass	Polyphenylsulfide	58%	Autoclave	PPS UD 58
Uni-directional	Glass	Polyphenylsulfide	40%	Autoclave	PPS UD 40
1/4 Satin	Glass	Polyphenylsulfide	53%	Autoclave	PPS 2 53
1/4 Satin	Glass	Polyphenylsulfide	52%	Autoclave	PPS 2 52
1/4 Satin	Glass	Polyphenylsulfide	40%	Autoclave	PPS 2 40
2x2 Twill	Carbon	Polyphenylsulfide	52%	Autoclave	PPS 3 52
Uni-directional	Glass	Polypropylene	58%	Autoclave	PP UD 58
Uni-directional	Glass	Polypropylene	40%	Autoclave	PP UD 40
1/4 Satin	Glass	Polypropylene	53%	Autoclave	PP 2 53
1/4 Satin	Glass	Polypropylene	49%	Hot-press	PP 2 HP 49
1/4 Satin	Glass	Polypropylene	48%	Autoclave	PP 2 48
1/4 Satin	Glass	Polypropylene	40%	Autoclave	PP 2 40
2x2 Twill	Carbon	Polypropylene	52%	Hot-press	PP 3 HP 52
2x2 Twill	Carbon	Polypropylene	48%	Autoclave	PP 3 48
1/4 Satin	Glass	Polycarbonate	50%	Autoclave	PC 2 50
2x2 Twill	Carbon	Polycarbonate	48%	Autoclave	PC 3 48

Table 4. Dependency of interlaminar shear strength on void content

Acronym	“A” Void free interlaminar shear strength [MPa]	“B” Dependency of void content [MPa/%]	Void content at full deconsolidation [%]	Interlaminar shear strength at full deconsolidation [MPa]
PPS UD 58	32.8	1.05	6.4	26.0
PPS UD 40	32.6	1.06	3.9	28.5
PPS 2 53	41.4	0.92	13.7	28.5
PPS 2 52	31.7	1.01	14.4	17.2
PPS 2 40	37.3	1.11	9.7	26.6
PPS 3 52	45.8	0.58	17.9	35.6
PP UD 58	7.3	0.51	2.8	5.8
PP UD 40	7.8	0.48	5.6	5.5
PP 2 53	17.2	0.54	18.8	7.0
PP 2 HP 49	17.3	0.46	11.4	12.1
PP 2 48	24.3	0.59	12.4	17.0
PP 2 40	18.7	0.81	7.5	10.5
PP 3 HP 52	21.7	0.51	18.3	12.4
PP 3 48	23.2	0.5	11.8	17.2
PC 2 50	55.4	1.35	11.5	37.9
PC 3 48	47.8	1.27	16.6	26.8

Table 5. Dependency of void content and interlaminar shear strength in the deconsolidated state

Parameter \ Property	Type reinforcement	Fiber volume fraction	Stacking sequence	Initial void content	Polymer strength	Manufacturing process
Void content	↑	↗	→	→	→	→
Interlaminar shear strength	↑	↗	↑	→	↑	→